

Stunting, oxidative stress, and neurogenesis potential of β -carotene and α -tocopherol: a mechanistic review

Nenni Dwi Aprianti Lubis^{1,2}

¹ Doctoral Program in Agricultural Science, Faculty of Agriculture, Universitas Sumatera Utara, Medan, Indonesia

² Department of Nutrition, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Sumatera Utara, Medan, Indonesia

³ Department of Food Science and Technology, Faculty of Agriculture, Universitas Sumatera Utara, Medan, Indonesia

⁴ Department of Pharmacology & Therapeutic, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Sumatera Utara, Medan, Indonesia

Corresponding author: Nenni Dwi Aprianti Lubis (nenni@usu.ac.id)

Received 8 September 2025 ♦ Accepted 6 October 2025 ♦ Published 21 October 2025

Citation: Lubis NDA, Julianti E, Sinaga H, Ichwan M (2025) Stunting, oxidative stress, and neurogenesis potential of β -carotene and α -tocopherol: a mechanistic review. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e171479>

Abstract

Stunting is associated with multiple comorbidities that significantly affect a child's future due to impaired neuronal development during the first 3 years of life. This disruption has long-term consequences on cognitive function, memory, and learning abilities. Oxidative stress plays a crucial role in exacerbating neuronal damage during malnutrition – underscoring the importance of interventions to prevent further harm. This review examines the neuroprotective effects of β -carotene and α -tocopherol, which are vitamin derivatives with strong antioxidant properties. These compounds help prevent oxidative damage through various mechanisms, promoting neurogenesis, reducing neuronal apoptosis, and enhancing neuroplasticity. Their supplementation may offer a potential approach to mitigating the neurological effects of malnutrition. However, there remains a lack of preclinical and clinical studies evaluating their role in preventing oxidative damage during early childhood malnutrition. Understanding the mechanisms by which β -carotene and α -tocopherol support neurodevelopment could provide insights into their potential benefits for children experiencing stunting-related oxidative stress.

Keywords

α -tocopherol, β -carotene, neurogenesis, oxidative stress, stunting

Introduction

Malnutrition and stunting remain significant global health challenges, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. Stunting, a condition resulting from chronic undernutrition, is defined as having a height-for-age that is below the median of two standard deviations based on the WHO Child Growth Standards. This condition arises from inadequate intake of nutrients

persisting for more than 24 months during critical periods of growth and development. According to WHO data, 22.2%, or 149 million children suffered from stunting in 2017, with South Asia contributing the highest prevalence, followed by Southeast Asia (United Nations Children's Fund et al. 2023). In Indonesia, the prevalence of stunting almost reached 21.6% in 2022, with severe stunting confirmed in 5.7% of children aged 0–59 months (Taufiqrokhman 2023).

The consequences of stunting extend beyond physical stature to affect brain development and cognitive abilities (Soliman et al. 2021). Chronic undernutrition during early life results in reduced brain growth, neuronal dysfunction, and impaired synaptic plasticity. These deficits predispose stunted children to lifelong cognitive and neurological challenges, limiting educational attainment, skill acquisition, and future socioeconomic opportunities (Dewey and Begum 2011). Such limitations affect individual potential and have broader societal impacts, perpetuating cycles of poverty and reduced economic productivity (Kustanto 2021). One critical pathway linking malnutrition to impaired brain function is oxidative stress. Stunting is closely associated with chronic undernutrition, which disrupts the balance between the production of free radicals and the body's ability to produce antioxidants (Samsonov and Urlacher 2025). This imbalance leads to oxidative stress, a condition that causes significant damage to cellular structures, including lipids, proteins, and DNA. Furthermore, oxidative stress impairs neuronal integrity, disrupts synaptic connectivity, and reduces neurogenesis in the central nervous system (CNS), ultimately contributing to the cognitive and developmental delays observed in stunted children (Yuan et al. 2015).

Carotenoids and α -tocopherol (vitamin E) are powerful antioxidants that maintain cellular health and mitigate the neurotoxic effects of oxidative stress. β -carotene is a crucial compound among carotenoids due to its potent antioxidant activity and ability to serve as a precursor to vitamin A, a nutrient essential for brain development and function. β -carotene plays a key role in neural tissues by neutralizing free radicals, thereby preventing oxidative damage that can compromise neuronal integrity (Gul et al. 2015). α -tocopherol, the most active form of vitamin E, complements these effects by protecting neuronal membranes from lipid peroxidation, ensuring cellular integrity and stability (Yamauchi 1997). Together, these compounds have garnered growing attention for their ability to prevent neurodegeneration and support neurodevelopment, particularly in high-risk individuals such as malnourished or stunted children.

Despite their recognized antioxidant benefits, the specific roles of β -carotene and α -tocopherol in supporting neurodevelopment in malnourished or stunted children remain insufficiently explored. Emerging evidence suggests that β -carotene and α -tocopherol may act as effective neuroprotective agents (Selvaraju et al. 2014; Magalingam et al. 2022). β -carotene reduces oxidative stress and enhances neurogenesis, while α -tocopherol protects neuronal membranes from lipid peroxidation, preserving cellular integrity. Additionally, β -carotene and α -tocopherol are complementary in regulating inflammation and enhancing synaptic plasticity, further strengthening their potential as therapeutic agents (Reiter et al. 2007; Yeh et al. 2009). This review evaluates current evidence on the neuroprotective effects of β -carotene and α -tocopherol in malnourished or stunted children. By synthesizing data from preclinical and clinical studies, this study aims

to clarify their roles in reducing oxidative stress and supporting cognitive development by inducing neurogenesis among stunted children. Furthermore, it highlights the importance of addressing malnutrition during critical developmental windows to prevent cognitive decline and improve long-term quality of life.

Materials and methods

This review was conducted as a scoping review to comprehensively map the available evidence on the mechanistic links between β -carotene and α -tocopherol in relation to stunting, oxidative stress, and neurogenesis. The methodological framework followed the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) Manual for Evidence Synthesis (2020) and is reported in accordance with the PRISMA-ScR (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews) checklist. Given the exploratory nature of scoping reviews, registration in PROSPERO was not applicable, as PROSPERO only accepts systematic reviews that address specific quantitative outcomes.

Search strategy

A comprehensive literature search was performed across multiple electronic databases from their inception until [insert final search date, e.g., 30 September 2025]. The databases included PubMed/MEDLINE, Embase, Scopus, Web of Science Core Collection, Cochrane Library, and CINAHL. Search terms combined controlled vocabulary (e.g., MeSH, Emtree) and free-text terms. Boolean operators and truncations were applied appropriately. Studies were selected based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria aligned with the Population–Concept–Context (PCC) framework recommended by JBI.

- **Population:** Human participants (particularly children), animal models, or in vitro neuronal systems.
- **Concept:** Investigations of β -carotene and/or α -tocopherol in relation to mechanisms of stunting, oxidative stress modulation, or neurogenesis.
- **Context:** Experimental, clinical, or mechanistic research providing biochemical, molecular, or physiological insights.

Study selection

All search results were imported into reference management software to remove duplicates. Titles and abstracts were screened independently by two reviewers according to the eligibility criteria. Full texts of potentially relevant studies were retrieved and assessed for inclusion. Discrepancies were resolved by consensus or consultation with a third reviewer. The screening process was summarized using a PRISMA-ScR flow diagram. The inclusion criteria encompassed original research articles, including clinical, animal, and cellular studies, that investigated the mech-

anistic roles of β -carotene and/or α -tocopherol. Eligible studies were required to report outcomes related to oxidative stress markers, neurogenesis indicators, or growth and stunting parameters relevant to developmental outcomes. Only publications written in English or those with English abstracts sufficient for accurate data interpretation were included. Conversely, reviews, editorials, commentaries, and conference abstracts without complete data were excluded. Studies that did not involve β -carotene or α -tocopherol as primary compounds of interest, purely epidemiological investigations lacking mechanistic insights, and case reports with fewer than 5 participants were also excluded. Non-peer-reviewed or low-quality sources that did not meet scientific rigor standards were similarly omitted from consideration.

Data charting and synthesis

A standardized data-charting form was developed based on the JBI template. Two reviewers independently extracted and charted relevant data, and disagreements were resolved through discussion. Extracted data were collated in structured tables for synthesis. Given the heterogeneity of study designs and outcomes, a descriptive thematic synthesis was employed. Data were grouped under three primary themes:

- Antioxidant and oxidative stress mechanisms of β -carotene and α -tocopherol;
- Neurogenesis and neuronal protection pathways;
- Nutritional and molecular associations with stunting and growth outcomes.

Findings were synthesized narratively and presented in tables highlighting mechanisms, experimental models, and outcomes. Quantitative pooling (meta-analysis) was not performed, as this review aimed to map the mechanistic landscape rather than estimate effect sizes.

How oxidative stress shapes the consequences of chronic undernutrition

Oxidative stress occurs when the production of reactive species – such as reactive oxygen species (ROS), reactive nitrogen species (RNS), and other free radicals – overwhelms the endogenous antioxidant defense system, leading to cellular damage. The primary source of these reactive species arises from mitochondrial metabolism, particularly during oxidative phosphorylation and electron transport chain activity. Because free radical production is an inherent byproduct of these essential metabolic processes, their formation in the human body must be counteracted by endogenous antioxidant capacity (Pizzino et al. 2017).

Emerging evidence highlights the potential long-term consequences of early-life oxidative stress. Exposure

during critical developmental stages, such as toddlerhood and adolescence, predisposes individuals to an increased risk of degenerative diseases later in life, including diabetes mellitus, Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, and autoimmune disorders (Yuan et al. 2015; Yang et al. 2020). Despite its significance, the study of oxidative stress during early life has been largely neglected, possibly due to the misconception that young individuals possess higher antioxidant capacity and therefore require no intervention. In a study evaluating total antioxidant capacity (TAC), age was not associated with assay results, underscoring the importance of antioxidant intervention across all age groups (Limberaki et al. 2012).

Oxidative stress plays a critical role in modulating cytokine production and regulating transcription factors, contributing to its impact on chronic undernutrition. In early life, oxidative stress can disrupt neuronal function, impair synaptic plasticity, and accelerate neurodegenerative processes, particularly in the developing brain (Salmina et al. 2021). Studies have demonstrated that stunted or undernourished children exhibit significantly reduced levels of endogenous antioxidants, including both enzymatic (e.g., superoxide dismutase [SOD], catalase [CAT], and glutathione peroxidase [GPx]) and non-enzymatic antioxidants (e.g., glutathione and coenzyme Q10) (Ghone et al. 2013; Aly et al. 2014; Arora et al. 2017; Saha et al. 2022). Concurrently, reactive species levels increase markedly in proportion to the severity and duration of undernutrition (Arora et al. 2017; Mastorci et al. 2017). These findings underscore the importance of investigating oxidative stress in the context of early-life exposure during undernutrition, as summarized in Table 1.

During undernutrition, the brain experiences a greater burden of oxidative damage due to its limited antioxidant systems while maintaining high cellular metabolism. Additionally, as a lipid-rich organ, the brain serves as a primary target for free radicals scavenging electrons (Salim 2017). Free radicals significantly disrupt various signaling pathways, leading to detrimental cellular events. In response to oxidative stress, molecular defense mechanisms are activated through a network of antioxidant systems primarily regulated by transcription factors. One of the key cellular pathways involves the activation of nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor (Nrf2) in response to elevated oxidative stress. Upon activation, Nrf2 binds to the antioxidant response element (ARE), a cis-regulatory element in the promoter regions of genes encoding major antioxidant enzymes, including SOD1, GPx1, CAT, and heme oxygenase (Ngo and Duennwald 2022). However, studies consistently report a significant reduction in the activation of these enzymes during undernutrition, while oxidative stress markers increase dramatically (Gavia-García et al. 2015; Aguilar et al. 2016), emphasizing the importance of high-burden oxidative stress among malnourished individuals.

Oxidative stress is a critical cellular event with profound neurotoxic effects. It contributes to various clinical manifestations, including cognitive delays, reduced learning capacity, memory deficits, and impaired executive functioning.

Table 1. Several studies evaluating oxidative stress among malnourished or stunted children.

Author, year	Title	Study design	Results	Comments
Ghone and Suryakar (2013)	A study of oxidative stress biomarkers and effect of oral antioxidant supplementation in severe acute malnutrition	This study was divided into two groups – healthy controls (60 children) and acutely malnourished children (60) – to evaluate oxidative stress and antioxidant status (serum MDA, serum zinc, erythrocyte superoxide dismutase [ESOD], and serum vitamin E). Participants received antioxidant syrup for 30 days.	Serum MDA, zinc, ESOD, and vitamin E levels differed between control and malnourished groups. Antioxidant syrup reduced MDA levels, increased serum zinc and ESOD, and did not affect vitamin E.	Antioxidant administration increased the endogenous antioxidant system but did not assess further implications regarding the dynamic balance of these substances.
Khare and Mohanty (2014)	Free radicals and antioxidant status in protein-energy malnutrition	This case-control study involved 250 children aged 6 months to 5 years: healthy (n = 57) and protein-energy malnutrition (PEM) children (65 mild, 60 moderate, 68 severe).	Erythrocyte glutathione (GSH), plasma Cu, Zn-superoxide dismutase, ceruloplasmin, and ascorbic acid were reduced in malnourished children (p < 0.000). Severe PEM was associated with lower serum antioxidant levels.	The study also provided evidence of free-radical activity by evaluating end-product oxidative stress markers (plasma MDA and protein carbonyl [PC]), explaining the reduced levels of endogenous antioxidants.
Aly and Shaalan (2014)	Oxidative stress status in nutritionally stunted children	This cross-sectional study included 50 stunted and 50 healthy children. Blood oxidative stress biomarkers – catalase, SOD, MDA, plasma GSH, total proteins, total antioxidant capacity (TAC), Cu, Zn, and vitamin C – were measured.	The stunted group showed lower antioxidant biomarkers but higher MDA levels than controls, with no correlation between stunting degree and oxidative markers.	Undernutrition (severe or mild) provokes oxidative stress. Vitamin C and Zn correlated with socioeconomic status, reflecting participants' dietary sufficiency.
Arora and Diwedi (2017)	A comparative assessment of serum malondialdehyde level and paraoxonase activity in healthy and kwashiorkor children	This case-control study compared malondialdehyde (MDA) and paraoxonase (PON-1) activity among 250 children with kwashiorkor and 125 healthy children.	MDA increased, while PON-1 decreased significantly in the kwashiorkor group (p < 0.001).	The study included many participants with kwashiorkor but assessed only two parameters (MDA and PON-1), limiting its interpretive value.
Saha and Mehndiratta (2021)	Oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, and premature aging in severe acute malnutrition in under-five children	This cross-sectional study compared 40 children with severe acute malnutrition (SAM) and 40 healthy controls, assessing total antioxidant status (TAOS), mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) content, and telomere length (TL).	Oxidative stress increased markedly among SAM children, who exhibited lower TAOS and higher mtDNA content. Telomere length did not differ between groups.	This study demonstrated that oxidative stress mainly originates from mitochondrial dysfunction, evidenced by increased mtDNA content in SAM children. However, it failed to show premature aging based on telomere length, which alone may not define aging.

Anatomically, the hippocampus, cerebellum, and amygdala are among the most vulnerable regions to oxidative damage, leading to significant impairments in their associated functions (Salim 2017). Within the hippocampus, the CA1 and CA3 regions, which form a crucial network between the dentate gyrus and the cornu ammonis, are particularly susceptible to oxidative stress. This region is essential for synaptic plasticity and regenerative processes and plays a pivotal role in learning and memory (Yin et al. 2017; Lana et al. 2020). Consequently, oxidative damage to this area disrupts cognitive functions and adaptive neural responses. Beyond the hippocampus, the prefrontal cortex (PFC) also undergoes structural and functional alterations in response to excessive oxidative stress. The PFC is integral to executive functions, and its impairment is strongly linked to cog-

nitive deficits. A scoping review highlights that oxidative stress contributes to hypomyelination within the PFC – a condition characterized by reduced myelin sheath formation. This process is primarily driven by oxidative damage to oligodendrocyte precursor cells responsible for myelin production in the central nervous system. The resulting hypomyelination further exacerbates cognitive impairments, emphasizing the critical role of oxidative stress in neurodevelopmental and cognitive disorders (Maas et al. 2017).

Across the reviewed studies, no clear dose-dependent effects or adverse outcomes of β -carotene and α -tocopherol supplementation were identified. Ghone and Suryakar (2013) reported that a 30-day oral antioxidant syrup containing these compounds reduced malondialdehyde (MDA) levels and improved antioxidant status in

Figure 1. Schematic overview of oxidative stress in stunted children, illustrating the molecular implications of signaling pathways that provoke neuronal and oxidative damage. BT, β -carotene; AT, α -tocopherol.

malnourished children, with no reported side effects, although only a single fixed dose was tested. Other studies, including those by Khare and Mohanty (2014), Aly and Shaalan (2014), Arora and Diwedi (2017), and Saha and Mehndiratta (2021), assessed oxidative stress and antioxidant imbalance in malnourished or stunted children without administering supplements. Collectively, available evidence supports the short-term safety and antioxidant benefits of β -carotene and α -tocopherol at physiological doses, but data on dose–response relationships and potential toxicity remain insufficient—underscoring the need for further controlled studies to determine safe and effective dosing in pediatric populations.

β -carotene as a natural antioxidant

β -carotene, a precursor to vitamin A, has garnered significant attention for its role in promoting neural growth and development. Acting as a potent antioxidant, β -carotene mitigates oxidative stress within neural tissues, safeguarding neurons from damage caused by free radicals. This antioxidative action is particularly vital in preventing the detrimental effects of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS), which are known to increase during periods of metabolic imbalance such as undernutrition (Ghone et al. 2013; Aly et al. 2014; Arora

et al. 2017; Miazek et al. 2022). In its classical mode of action, β -carotene functions as a free radical scavenger due to its conjugated double-bond structure, which allows it to quench singlet oxygen and other reactive species (Veltri 2024). By reducing oxidative stress, β -carotene protects cellular components, including lipids, proteins, and DNA, from oxidative modifications that could otherwise impair neural structure and function. During undernutrition, the heightened production of ROS and RNS exacerbates oxidative damage and disrupts cellular homeostasis (Baliga et al. 2019).

The polyene structure of β -carotene plays a central role in its antioxidant activity, enabling it to scavenge free radicals effectively through three key mechanisms (Pisoschi and Pop 2015). First, radical addition occurs when free radicals directly interact with the conjugated polyene structure of β -carotene. Its long chain of conjugated double bonds provides a stable environment for radicals by delocalizing the unpaired electron, thereby neutralizing their reactivity. Second, electron transfer allows β -carotene to act as an electron donor, converting free radicals into less reactive species and preventing oxidative chain reactions (Ribeiro et al. 2018). However, this process can act as a double-edged sword, as it may generate a carotenoid radical cation (Car^+), which requires further neutralization by other antioxidants such as α -tocopherol (vitamin E) or vitamin C (Mendiara and Perissinotti 2017). Third, β -carotene participates in al-

lylic hydrogen donation, where hydrogens from carbon atoms adjacent to double bonds are transferred to free radicals. This stabilizes the radical, forming a carotenoid radical that does not promote further oxidative damage. While β -carotene primarily functions as an antioxidant, under conditions of high oxidative stress it may exhibit pro-oxidant activity, potentially exacerbating oxidative damage depending on environmental factors (Prasad et al. 2011; Rohmah et al. 2022).

The antioxidant activity of β -carotene has been extensively documented in various studies, demonstrating its effectiveness in neutralizing free radicals and producing cleavage products that contribute to its protective effects. A study utilizing 2,2'-azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS) and 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assays showed that β -carotene exhibits potent antioxidant activity compared with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), Trolox (T), butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT), and α -tocopherol (vitamin E). This activity was further enhanced by incorporating β -carotene-loaded nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) derived from a mixture of palm olein and stearin (Zhao et al. 2016). Another study reported that the radical scavenging activity of β -carotene reached 85% in an ABTS assay using extracts from *Lycium barbarum* L. and *Canarium odontophyllum* (Mueller and Boehm 2011; Pardede et al. 2024). Similarly, studies on *Baccaurea costulata* and *Baccaurea motleyana* fruits confirmed the antioxidant effects of β -carotene through DPPH, oxygen radical absorbance capacity (ORAC), total reactive antioxidant potential (TRAP), and ABTS assays. These findings demonstrated strong quenching and scavenging activity, with a positive correlation ($r = 0.9$) between β -carotene levels and its radical scavenging ability (Abrego-Guandique et al. 2023). Additionally, research on β -carotene isomers and their metabolites has indicated significant antioxidant activity through various assays, including ABTS bleaching, ferric-reducing antioxidant power (FRAP), and radical scavenging tests, where β -carotene has shown higher antioxidant potential than α -tocopherol (Park et al. 2020).

Although β -carotene is widely recognized as a potent antioxidant capable of quenching singlet oxygen and neutralizing reactive oxygen species, it can, under certain conditions, exhibit pro-oxidant behavior that contributes to oxidative damage rather than protection. This paradoxical shift is primarily influenced by environmental and physiological factors that alter its redox balance. High oxygen tension, such as that found in pulmonary tissue or under hyperoxic conditions, promotes the reaction of β -carotene radicals with molecular oxygen, leading to the formation of peroxy radicals and oxidative by-products. Similarly, excessive or supraphysiological doses of β -carotene increase the likelihood of carotenoid-carotenoid and carotenoid-radical interactions, producing unstable radical cations and breakdown products that can initiate lipid peroxidation. This effect is further exacerbated in individuals exposed to strong pro-oxidant stressors such as cigarette smoke, alcohol, or environmental pollutants,

where abundant reactive radicals directly oxidize β -carotene into electrophilic degradation products, including β -apo-carotenals and epoxides. The pro-oxidant shift is also observed when essential co-antioxidants such as vitamin C, vitamin E, or glutathione are depleted. These molecules normally regenerate β -carotene from its radical form; in their absence, carotenoid radicals persist and propagate oxidative chain reactions. Transition metal ions such as iron and copper further amplify this process by catalyzing Fenton-type reactions that generate hydroxyl radicals, while ultraviolet or high-energy light exposure promotes β -carotene photooxidation, yielding singlet oxygen and reactive intermediates. Within lipid-rich environments – particularly membranes containing high levels of polyunsaturated fatty acids – β -carotene radicals can abstract hydrogen atoms and trigger lipid peroxidation cascades (Shin et al. 2020a).

Molecular insights: β -carotene as a driver of neural growth

β -carotene can influence neurogenesis, neuronal survival, differentiation, and synaptic plasticity, primarily through its interaction with retinoic acid at the genetic level. β -carotene exerts its beneficial effects by serving as a precursor to retinoic acid, which regulates the transcription of genes essential for brain development and function. It also possesses strong antioxidant properties that help combat oxidative stress, reduce neuronal damage, and support cognitive function (Park et al. 2020; Abrego-Guandique et al. 2023). Studies have shown that β -carotene administration enhances the expression of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) – a key protein involved in neuroplasticity – leading to improved neurological and behavioral outcomes (Avraham et al. 2019, 2021). This neurotrophic factor primarily mediates the neurogenesis effect of β -carotene under pro-oxidative conditions.

β -carotene is transformed into two retinal molecules by β , β -carotene-15,15'-monooxygenase (BCMO I), after which the process converts retinal molecules into retinoic acid (RA) and retinol, serving as vitamin A derivatives (Eroglu and Harrison 2013). Meanwhile, β -carotene demonstrates potent provitamin A activity compared with other carotenoids, which mainly have biological implications through the production of retinoic acid. Retinoic acid is involved in various biological processes within the human body. It serves as a ligand for two types of nuclear receptors – retinoid X receptors (RXRs) and retinoic acid receptors (RARs). RARs have a higher affinity for (all-E)- β -carotene, a precursor of (all-E)-retinoic acid (RA), whereas RXRs demonstrate a strong affinity for (9Z)- β -carotene, a precursor of (9Z)-retinoic acid (RA) (Grune et al. 2010). These two nuclear receptors regulate the transcription of genes essential for neuronal survival, growth, and differentiation. They undergo dimerization and modulate retinoic acid response elements, which support neuroprotection against free

radicals (Le Maire et al. 2012). These genes include those encoding neurotrophic factors such as BDNF, which further support the survival and maturation of neurons (Kurauchi et al. 2011; Mey 2017).

Oxidative stress plays a central role in neuronal damage during malnutrition, leading to serious consequences. Reducing oxidative stress with antioxidant agents can help mitigate several signaling cascades that disrupt metabolic pathways and induce neuronal apoptosis. In animal models, β -carotene has demonstrated strong antioxidant activity by enhancing the retention of endogenous antioxidant enzymes within the intracellular environment, such as superoxide dismutase and glutathione (Hira et al. 2019). It also upregulates key proteins, including nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (Nrf2) and antioxidant response genes that encode endogenous antioxidant enzymes such as NADPH quinone oxidoreductase and heme oxygenase-1 (Chen et al. 2019). Another study showed that β -carotene administration increased BDNF expression levels in mice, promoting neuroplasticity, as evidenced by improved social interaction and communication behaviors (Avraham et al. 2019). Furthermore, β -carotene specifically enhanced BDNF gene expression in the hippocampus and hypothalamus, which correlated with improved neurological and behavioral scores in mice (Avraham et al. 2021). This process is further visualized in Fig. 2.

BDNF is a major neurotrophic factor in the central nervous system, and its upregulation is associated with the activation of three major signaling pathways: MAPK/ERK, PLC γ , and PI3K. These pathways regulate key neurological functions, including neuronal survival, differentiation, and synaptic plasticity (Singh et al. 2025). Upon binding to its receptor, tropomyosin-related kinase receptor B (TrkB), BDNF induces receptor homodimerization, initiating downstream signaling cascades (Wang et al. 2024). These pathways play a crucial role in neuroplasticity and neurogenesis, and dysregulation of BDNF signaling has been implicated in various neurological disorders. Reduced BDNF levels are associated with neuronal dysfunction and an increased risk of apoptosis. Among these pathways, MAPK/ERK signaling facilitates neuronal proliferation and neurogenesis, primarily by activating the transcription factor cAMP response element-binding protein (CREB) (Iroegbu et al. 2021). CREB phosphorylation and sustained BDNF signaling are essential for memory formation (Finkbeiner et al. 1997). Meanwhile, the PI3K/Akt pathway is crucial for neuronal survival and growth, exerting its dual effects through several transcription factors by attenuating NF- κ B and FoxO3a while increasing the BCL2 family proteins (Kalinichenko et al. 2020; Guo et al. 2024).

However, the effects of β -carotene on cellular growth have been a subject of ongoing debate due to evidence from earlier studies linking β -carotene to paradoxical outcomes. Notably, some studies have associated high β -carotene intake with an increased risk of lung cancer in heavy smokers and individuals with asbestosis (RR

Figure 2. β -carotene mechanistic diagram. β -carotene primarily acts as a ligand for the nuclear receptors RXR and RAR, contributing to BDNF upregulation. Retinol is converted into retinoic acid, which then binds to RAR and RXR in the nucleus, synergistically enhancing BDNF expression. Abbreviations: BDNF, brain-derived neurotrophic factor; RA, retinoic acid; RAR, retinoic acid receptor; RAREs, retinoic acid response elements; RXR, retinoid X receptor; STRA6, signaling receptor and transporter of retinol.

1.16 and 1.21, respectively) (Kordiak et al. 2022). This paradox is hypothesized to arise from β -carotene's ability to modulate redox-sensitive signaling pathways that influence cell cycle progression and apoptosis. The dual effects of β -carotene on cell growth stem from its potential to act as both an antioxidant and a pro-oxidant. Under certain conditions, β -carotene can become an endogenous producer of free radicals. This occurs through mechanisms such as the induction of cytochrome P450 isoforms, which catalyze metabolic processes that generate ROS, as well as the promotion of Fenton reactions and auto-oxidation of β -carotene. These processes may produce oxidative carotenoid derivatives and other reactive species that can disrupt cellular homeostasis and provoke oxidative damage (Palozza 2005). Nevertheless, the pro-oxidant effects of β -carotene are largely dose-dependent and context-specific rather than an inherent detrimental property. In non-smokers and under physiological conditions, β -carotene primarily functions as an antioxidant, reducing oxidative stress and supporting cellular homeostasis (Shin et al. 2020b). Additionally, its

redox-modulating properties may contribute to adaptive cellular responses and potential therapeutic applications in controlled settings (Palozza et al. 2003).

Impairment of inflammatory signaling induced by β -carotene

Increased inflammatory activity exacerbates neural damage and disrupts neurogenesis during states of undernutrition or malnutrition. Chronic inflammation increases the production of pro-inflammatory mediators, such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6, which exacerbate oxidative stress and hinder neuronal development (Wu et al. 2023). β -carotene's dual antioxidative and anti-inflammatory mechanisms combat this detrimental cycle synergistically. β -carotene helps restore the balance necessary for effective neurogenesis and synaptic remodeling by mitigating inflammation and reducing oxidative damage. This action is crucial for maintaining neural plasticity and promoting recovery during nutritional rehabilitation. However, the anti-inflammatory properties of β -carotene present a double-edged sword – on one side, it can repress inflammatory cytokines, while on the other, under certain conditions, it can increase cytokine production, causing additional damage. In a dose-dependent manner, a study concluded that a dose of 2 μ M β -carotene reduced the inflammatory response, while 20 μ M upregulated IL-8 and TNF- α production (Yeh et al. 2009).

Meanwhile, β -carotene enhanced the expression of inflammation-related genes in hyperglycemic conditions, such as IL31RA, CD38, and NCF1B, in a study using THP-1 cells – a human monocytic leukemia cell line – at lower doses ranging from 0.5 to 5 μ M (Kondo et al. 2022). In contrast, MAPK signaling pathways associated with inflammatory cytokine gene expression were repressed following β -carotene administration (25 μ M), indicating that this compound blunts TNF- α -induced intestinal inflammation and injury (Song et al. 2024). In another animal model, oxidative stress induced by acute spinal cord injury (SCI) was successfully treated with β -carotene administration, resulting in reduced inflammatory markers (TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-18, and cyclooxygenase-2) and regulated production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and malondialdehyde. Subsequent analysis revealed that β -carotene administration repressed the NF- κ B signaling pathway, which activates the transcription of pro-inflammatory genes (Zhou et al. 2018).

The dual function of β -carotene as both an antioxidant and an anti-inflammatory agent was also demonstrated in a study conducted using mesenchymal stem cells. ROS levels and MDA were significantly reduced following β -carotene administration, accompanied by a decrease in IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α levels. This was also confirmed by the reduction of NF- κ B phosphorylation and the KAT7-P15 axis, which implies an anti-aging process in the stem cells (Zheng et al. 2022). These molecular mechanisms underscore β -carotene's therapeutic promise

in addressing neurological conditions linked to oxidative stress, impaired neurogenesis, and inflammation. By supporting both the structural and functional aspects of neural growth, β -carotene plays a crucial role in fostering a resilient and adaptive nervous system, particularly during critical developmental periods and in response to environmental challenges.

α -tocopherol: the mechanism of action against free radicals

Several studies have confirmed that α -tocopherol deficiency exacerbates lipid peroxidation and leads to metabolic derangement, emphasizing its critical role in cellular protection. This deficiency can arise as early as embryogenesis, particularly in cases of malnutrition, which is strongly associated with increased oxidative stress (Lebold and Traber 2014). As the most biologically active form of vitamin E, α -tocopherol is a key antioxidant, shielding cell membranes – rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids – from oxidative damage (Manolescu et al. 2008). Unlike other tocopherol and tocotrienol derivatives, α -tocopherol is strictly regulated by the α -tocopherol transfer protein (α -TTP), and mutations in this protein can lead to severe vitamin E deficiency. While α -tocopherol exhibits moderate antioxidant activity compared with other tocopherols and tocotrienols, it is the most abundant and active form among vitamin E analogues, reinforcing its use as a supplement in specific conditions (Arai and Kono 2021). Additionally, its lipid-soluble nature enables it to integrate into cellular membranes, providing antioxidant protection in regions inaccessible to polar antioxidants such as vitamin C and glutathione (Atkinson et al. 2010).

One of the most notable mechanisms of the antioxidant activity of α -tocopherol is the chain-breaking mechanism against lipid peroxidation. Lipid peroxidation occurs in three steps: initiation, propagation, and termination. During initiation, free radicals attack the doubly allylic hydrogen of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) to form lipid radicals (L \bullet) and water. L \bullet is an unstable molecule that reacts rapidly with oxygen to produce lipid peroxyl radicals (LOO \bullet), which subsequently attack other PUFAs to form new lipid radicals – constituting the propagation phase (Traber and Atkinson 2007). This vicious chain reaction continues until it generates inactive products, marking the termination phase. α -tocopherol acts as an electron donor via its phenolic hydrogen to peroxyl radicals, thereby preventing the continuation of the propagation step. This process makes α -tocopherol a chain-breaking antioxidant (Manolescu et al. 2008). The involvement of α -tocopherol results in the formation of hydroperoxide, a neutral and stable lipid product, and the α -tocopheroxyl radical (α -TO \bullet), which is less reactive and can be recycled back to α -tocopherol through other antioxidant activities. One tocopherol molecule can scavenge two peroxyl radicals, a measure representing the antioxidant efficiency of α -tocopherol (Yamauchi 2007).

Ohkatsu et al. (2001) conducted a study evaluating several tocopherols and demonstrated the antioxidant power ranking δ - > α - > β - > γ -tocopherols based on the rate constant of inhibition in radical chain reactions (K_{inh}), making α -tocopherol the most important and abundant vitamin E analogue. In another study, RSL-3 (a glutathione peroxidase 4 inhibitor)-treated human hepatocytes showed successful suppression of intracellular reactive oxygen species following the administration of α -tocopherol and 6-hydroxymethyl tocopherol (HMTc; synthetic α -tocopherol). This study also demonstrated the impact of vitamin E on several gene expressions through independent antioxidant mechanisms (Chen et al. 2025). Palm vitamin E, consisting of 30% tocopherols and 70% tocotrienols, has exhibited antioxidant activity through DPPH scavenging, with a positive correlation between scavenging capacity and concentration (Selamat et al. 2018). Meanwhile, computational analysis revealed that α -tocopherol exhibits higher antioxidant activity than Trolox, as well as a protective effect against free-radical-induced stress (Thbayh et al. 2024).

α -tocopherol-induced benefits in neurogenesis

Experimental studies have shown that α -tocopherol promotes neuroprotection and reduces morbidity and mortality among rodent offspring. Adequate intake of α -tocopherol has been linked to a reduced risk of embryonic abnormalities and a protective effect against brain atrophy and neuronal degeneration (Cecchini et al. 2003; Lebold and Traber 2014). The brain is highly susceptible to oxidative stress due to its abundance of unsaturated fatty acids and its exclusive reliance on α -tocopherol as the primary form of vitamin E, with negligible amounts of tocotrienols. This unique composition highlights the crucial role of α -tocopherol in safeguarding the brain against oxidative damage (Jelinek et al. 2021). Consequently, α -tocopherol deficiency has been linked to an increased risk of neurological diseases, as it serves as the brain's major antioxidant (Ulatowski and Manor 2013).

α -tocopherol is a lipid-soluble compound that can exert intracellular signaling effects impacting gene expression, mainly via redox-sensitive transcription factors such as Nrf2 (Azzi 2007; Fernandes et al. 2020; Brigelius-Flohé 2021; Chen et al. 2025). Other non-oxidative pathways of α -tocopherol include the activation of protein phosphatase 2A, reduction of protein kinase C (PKC) activity, and prevention of Akt-PKH dephosphorylation. α -tocopherol, known for its role as a ligand for the nuclear receptor PXR, is responsible for lipid metabolism and other protein expressions. A study conducted in a rat model showed that α -tocopherol supplementation acts as an exogenous factor promoting hippocampal dentate gyrus neurogenesis, as evidenced by cell refinement and increased expression of immature neuron markers (PSA-NCAM and DCX) in both immature and mature neurons – highlighting α -tocopherol-induced dentate gyrus neuroplasticity (Cecchini et al. 2003). In another experiment, α -tocopherol exhibited

protective effects by reducing neuronal apoptosis but inhibiting cell proliferation, suggesting a neuroprotective rather than a proliferative role (Cuppini et al. 2001). Similarly, the antioxidant activity of α -tocopherol promoted memory and motor improvements while inducing neurotrophic components that subsequently acted as neuroregenerative agents (Gugliandolo et al. 2017). In a mechanistic model, α -tocopherol increased BDNF via the BDNF-TrkB-CREB pathway in the hippocampus and cortex of a phenytoin-induced cognitive impairment rat model, which correlated with improved behavioral performance (Nagib et al. 2019).

In another study, α -tocopherol inhibited inflammatory signaling through its actions on the Nrf2 and NF- κ B pathways and by directly inhibiting cyclooxygenase-2 and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) (Jiang et al. 2000; Elisia and Kitts 2015; Wallert et al. 2019). This anti-inflammatory mechanism is largely attributed to its suppressive effect on microglial activation. One study demonstrated that brain α -tocopherol levels were negatively correlated with total microglial density (de Leeuw et al. 2020), which is considered a non-antioxidant effect of α -tocopherol. Specifically, α -tocopherol prevents NF- κ B translocation to the nucleus and inhibits c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK) phosphorylation, thereby preventing pro-inflammatory cytokine transcription (Lee and Kim 2024). Clinical studies have also reported that α -tocopherol administration reduces the levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α) and acute-phase proteins such as C-reactive protein (Singh and Jialal 2004). Microglial expansion has been identified as a marker of immune activation in the central nervous system, polarizing cells into an inflammatory phenotype. This phenomenon reduces cell proliferation, survival, and function during neurogenesis. The immune system also influences adult hippocampal neurogenesis and diminishes neural plasticity (Kohman and Rhodes 2013). All these effects are further visualized in Fig. 3.

Conclusion

β -carotene and α -tocopherol act synergistically to mitigate oxidative damage in neuronal tissues, with β -carotene effectively quenching singlet oxygen and α -tocopherol inhibiting lipid peroxidation within cellular membranes. Together, these antioxidants may enhance neuroprotection in malnourished children by reducing oxidative stress, preserving neuronal integrity, and supporting neurodevelopmental processes. However, a critical appraisal of current recommendations for early supplementation reveals that empirical support remains limited and often derived from small-scale or heterogeneous studies. Evidence regarding optimal dosing, timing of intervention, and long-term neurological outcomes remains insufficient, while the potential for β -carotene to exhibit pro-oxidant effects under certain conditions warrants caution. Moreover, most available data focus on surrogate oxidative biomarkers rather than direct measures of neurogenesis or cognitive function. Future research should prioritize well-designed

Figure 3. α -tocopherol mechanistic diagram. Grey-shaded boxes represent four major mechanisms of α -tocopherol influence on neurogenesis. It activates the Nrf2-ARE pathway, enhancing endogenous antioxidant enzyme expression; induces PP2A activation to stabilize the cytoskeleton and improve neuronal integrity; reduces PKC activity while maintaining Akt phosphorylation, thereby stimulating mTOR and CREB pathways leading to BDNF upregulation; and scavenges ROS during lipid peroxidation. Abbreviations: Akt-PKH, protein kinase B/protein kinase H; ARE, antioxidant response element; BDNF, brain-derived neurotrophic factor; CREB, cAMP response element-binding protein; mTOR, mechanistic target of rapamycin; Nrf2, nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2; PKC, protein kinase C; PP2A, protein phosphatase 2A; PXR, pregnane X receptor; TrkB, tropomyosin receptor kinase B.

randomized controlled trials that assess dose-response relationships, synergistic interactions between β -carotene and α -tocopherol, and their mechanistic links to neurodevelopmental and clinical outcomes. Addressing these gaps will be crucial to establish evidence-based guidelines for safe and effective antioxidant supplementation in early life and malnourished populations.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

The authors acknowledge the use of generative AI tools such as DeepL and ChatGPT from OpenAI, which were used specifically to assist with language editing and grammar correction in the preparation of this manuscript. The authors did not use AI tools to create content or interpret data. The authors take full responsibility for the content and conclusions written in this manuscript.

Funding

This research was funded by the Directorate of Research and Community Service (DPPM), Directorate General of Research

and Development, Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology (Kemdiktisaintek), through the Doctoral Dissertation Research Scheme.

Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Nenni Dwi Aprianti Lubis <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9386-9810>

Elisa Julianti <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7199-3220>

Hotnida Sinaga <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7136-7895>

Muhammad Ichwan <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8380-9099>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Abrego-Guandique DM, Bonet ML, Caroleo MC, Cannataro R, Tucci P, Ribot J, Cione E (2023) The Effect of Beta-Carotene on Cognitive Function: A Systematic Review. *Brain Sciences* 13(10): 1468. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci13101468>
- Aguilar TAF, Navarro BCH, Pérez JAM (2016) Endogenous Antioxidants: A Review of their Role in Oxidative Stress. In: *A Master Regulator of Oxidative Stress - The Transcription Factor Nrf2*. InTech. <https://doi.org/10.5772/65715>
- Aly GS, Shaalan AH, Mattar MK, Ahmed HH, Zaki ME, Abdallah HR (2014) Oxidative stress status in nutritionally stunted children. *Egyptian Pediatric Association Gazette* 62(1): 28–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epag.2014.02.003>
- Arai H, Kono N (2021) α -Tocopherol transfer protein (α -TTP). *Free Radical Biology and Medicine* 176: 162–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2021.09.021>
- Arora R, Diwedi J, Mishra SP (2017) A Comparative Assessment of Serum Malondialdehyde Level and Paraoxonase Activity in Healthy and Kwashiorkor Children. *National Journal of Laboratory Medicine* 6: 4–6.
- Atkinson J, Harroun T, Wassall SR, Stillwell W, Katsaras J (2010) The location and behavior of α tocopherol in membranes. *Molecular Nutrition & Food Research* 54: 641–651. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mnfr.200900439>
- Avraham Y, Berry EM, Donskoy M, Ahmad WA, Vorobiev L, Albeck A, Mankuta D (2019) Beta-carotene as a novel therapy for the treatment of “Autistic like behavior” in animal models of Autism. *Behavioural Brain Research* 364: 469–479. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbr.2017.09.041>
- Avraham Y, Mankuta D, Lipsker L, Vorobiev L, Patael S, Hassid G, Berry EM, Albeck A (2021) Beta-Carotene derivatives as novel therapy for the prevention and treatment of autistic symptoms. *Bioorganic Chemistry* 115: 105224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioorg.2021.105224>
- Azzi A (2007) Molecular mechanism of α -tocopherol action. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine* 43(1): 16–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2007.03.013>
- Baliga MS, Shivashankara AR, Venkatesh S, Bhat HP, Palatty PL, Bhandari G, Rao S (2019) Phytochemicals in the Prevention of Ethanol-Induced Hepatotoxicity: A Revisit. In: *Dietary Interventions in Liver Disease: Foods, Nutrients, and Dietary Supplements*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-814466-4.00007-0>
- Brigelius-Flohé R (2021) Vitamin E research: Past, now and future. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine* 177: 381–390. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2021.10.029>
- Cecchini T, Ciaroni S, Ferri P, Ambrogini P, Cuppini R, Santi S, Del Grande P (2003) α -tocopherol, an exogenous factor of adult hippocampal neurogenesis regulation. *Journal of Neuroscience Research* 73(4): 447–455. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jnr.10690>
- Chen M, Ghelfi M, Poon J-F, Jeon N, Boccalon N, Rubsamén M, Valentino S, Mehta V, Stamper M, Tariq H, Zunica E, Ulatowski L, Chung S, Fritz C, Cameron M, Cameron C, Pratt DA, Atkinson J, Finno CJ, Manor D (2025) Antioxidant-independent activities of α -tocopherol. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 301: 108327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbc.2025.108327>
- Chen P, Li L, Gao Y, Xie Z, Zhang Y, Pan Z, Tu Y, Wang H, Han Q, Hu X, Xin X (2019) β -carotene provides neuroprotection after experimental traumatic brain injury via the Nrf2-ARE pathway. *Journal of Integrative Neuroscience* 18(2): 153–161. <https://doi.org/10.31083/j.jin.2019.02.120>
- Cuppini R, Ciaroni S, Cecchini T, Ambrogini P, Ferri P, Del Grande P, Papa S (2001) α -Tocopherol controls cell proliferation in the adult rat dentate gyrus. *Neuroscience Letters* 303(3): 198–200. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3940\(01\)01747-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3940(01)01747-5)
- de Leeuw FA, Schneider JA, Agrawal S, Leurgans SE, Morris MC (2020) Brain tocopherol levels are associated with lower activated microglia density in elderly human cortex. *Alzheimer's & Dementia: Translational Research & Clinical Interventions* 6(1): e12021. <https://doi.org/10.1002/trc2.12021>
- Dewey KG, Begum K (2011) Long-term consequences of stunting in early life. *Maternal and Child Nutrition* 7(s3): 5–18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1740-8709.2011.00349.x>
- Elisia I, Kitts DD (2015) Tocopherol isoforms (α -, γ -, and δ -) show distinct capacities to control Nrf-2 and Nf κ B signaling pathways that modulate inflammatory response in Caco-2 intestinal cells. *Molecular and Cellular Biochemistry* 404: 123–131. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11010-015-2372-8>
- Eroglu A, Harrison EH (2013) Carotenoid metabolism in mammals, including man: Formation, occurrence, and function of apocarotenoids. *Journal of Lipid Research* 54(7): 1719–1730. <https://doi.org/10.1194/jlr.R039537>
- Fernandes VAR, Netto RORE, Belozo FL, Caldeira EJ (2020) Anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects of using α -tocopherol in cell culture of the parotid gland under conditions similar to diabetes mellitus. *Romanian Journal of Diabetes, Nutrition and Metabolic Diseases* 27.
- Finkbeiner S, Tavazoie SF, Maloratsky A, Jacobs KM, Harris KM, Greenberg ME (1997) CREB: A major mediator of neuronal neurotrophin responses. *Neuron* 19(5): 1031–1047. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0896-6273\(00\)80395-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0896-6273(00)80395-5)
- Gavia-García G, González-Martínez H, Miliar-García Á, Bonilla-González E, de los Ángeles Rosas-Trejo M, Königsberg M,

- Nájera-Medina O, Luna-López A, González-Torres MC (2015) Oxidative damage and antioxidant defense in thymus of malnourished lactating rats. *Nutrition* 31(11–12): 1408–1415. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nut.2015.05.014>
- Ghone RA, Suryakar AN, Kulhalli PM, Bhagat SS, Padalkar RK, Karnik AC, Hundekar PS, Sangle DA (2013) A study of oxidative stress biomarkers and effect of oral antioxidant supplementation in severe acute malnutrition. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research* 7(10): 2146–2148. <https://doi.org/10.7860/JCDR/2013/6019.3454>
- Grune T, Lietz G, Palou A, Ross AC, Stahl W, Tang G, Thurnham D, Yin SA, Biesalski HK (2010) β -carotene is an important vitamin A source for humans. *Journal of Nutrition* 140(12): 2268S–2285S. <https://doi.org/10.3945/jn.109.119024>
- Gugliandolo A, Bramanti P, Mazzon E (2017) Role of vitamin e in the treatment of alzheimer's disease: Evidence from animal models. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 18(12): 2504. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms18122504>
- Gul K, Tak A, Singh AK, Singh P, Yousuf B, Wani AA (2015) Chemistry, encapsulation, and health benefits of β -carotene – A review. *Cogent Food and Agriculture* 1: 1018696. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311932.2015.1018696>
- Guo N, Wang X, Xu M, Bai J, Yu H, Le Z (2024) PI3K/AKT signaling pathway: Molecular mechanisms and therapeutic potential in depression. *Pharmacological Research* 206: 107300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phrs.2024.107300>
- Hira S, Saleem U, Anwar F, Sohail MF, Raza Z, Ahmad B (2019) β -Carotene: A Natural Compound Improves Cognitive Impairment and Oxidative Stress in a Mouse Model of Streptozotocin-Induced Alzheimer's Disease. *Biomolecules* 9(9): 441. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom9090441>
- Iroegbu JD, Ijomone OK, Femi-Akinlosotu OM, Ijomone OM (2021) ERK/MAPK signalling in the developing brain: Perturbations and consequences. *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews* 131: 792–805. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2021.10.009>
- Jelinek M, Jurajda M, Duris K (2021) Oxidative stress in the brain: Basic concepts and treatment strategies in stroke. *Antioxidants* 10(12): 1886. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox10121886>
- Jiang Q, Elson-Schwab I, Courtemanche C, Ames BN (2000) γ -Tocopherol and its major metabolite, in contrast to α -tocopherol, inhibit cyclooxygenase activity in macrophages and epithelial cells. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 97(21): 11494–11499. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.200357097>
- Kalinichenko SG, Matveeva NY, Korobtsov AV (2020) Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor (BDNF) As a Regulator of Apoptosis under Conditions of Focal Experimental Stroke. *Bulletin of Experimental Biology and Medicine* 169: 701–706. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10517-020-04959-7>
- Kohman RA, Rhodes JS (2013) Neurogenesis, inflammation and behavior. *Brain, Behavior, and Immunity* 27: 22–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbi.2012.09.003>
- Kondo S, Suzuki R, Nakashima Y, Mochizuki K (2022) β -Carotene enhances the expression of inflammation-related genes and histone H3 K9 acetylation, K4 dimethylation, and K36 trimethylation around these genes in juvenile macrophage-like THP-1 cells. *Biochemistry and Biophysics Reports* 31: 101325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrep.2022.101325>
- Kordiak J, Bielec F, Jabłoński S, Pastuszek-Lewandoska D (2022) Role of Beta-Carotene in Lung Cancer Primary Chemoprevention: A Systematic Review with Meta-Analysis and Meta-Regression. *Nutrients* 14(7): 1361. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu14071361>
- Kurauchi Y, Hisatsune A, Isohama Y, Sawa T, Akaike T, Shudo K, Katsuki H (2011) Midbrain dopaminergic neurons utilize nitric oxide/cyclic GMP signaling to recruit ERK that links retinoic acid receptor stimulation to up-regulation of BDNF. *Journal of Neurochemistry* 116(3): 323–333. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-4159.2010.06916.x>
- Kustanto A (2021) The Prevalence Of Stunting, Poverty, And Economic Growth In Indonesia: A Panel Data Dynamic Causality Analysis. *Journal of Developing Economies* 6(2): 150–173. <https://doi.org/10.20473/jde.v6i2.22358>
- Lana D, Ugolini F, Giovannini MG (2020) An Overview on the Differential Interplay Among Neurons–Astrocytes–Microglia in CA1 and CA3 Hippocampus in Hypoxia/Ischemia. *Frontiers in Cellular Neuroscience* 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncel.2020.585833>
- le Maire A, Alvarez S, Shankaranarayanan P, R de Lera A, Bourguet W, Gronemeyer H (2012) Retinoid Receptors and Therapeutic Applications of RAR/RXR Modulators. *Current Topics in Medicinal Chemistry* 12(6): 505–527. <https://doi.org/10.2174/156802612799436687>
- Lebold KM, Traber MG (2014) Interactions between α -tocopherol, polyunsaturated fatty acids, and lipoxygenases during embryogenesis. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine* 66: 13–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2013.07.039>
- Lee S, Kim H-K (2024) α -Tocopherol and γ -tocopherol decrease inflammatory response and insulin resistance during the interaction of adipocytes and macrophages. *Nutrition Research and Practice* 18: 761. <https://doi.org/10.4162/nrp.2024.18.6.761>
- Limberaki E, Eleftheriou PH, Vagdatli E, Kostoglou V, Petrou CH (2012) Serum antioxidant status among young, middle-aged and elderly people before and after antioxidant rich diet. *Hippokratia* 16.
- Maas DA, Vallès A, Martens GJM (2017) Oxidative stress, prefrontal cortex hypomyelination and cognitive symptoms in schizophrenia. *Translational Psychiatry* 7: 1171. <https://doi.org/10.1038/TP.2017.138>
- Magalingam KB, Somanath SD, Haleagrahara N, Selvaduray KR, Radhakrishnan AK (2022) Unravelling the neuroprotective mechanisms of carotenes in differentiated human neural cells: Biochemical and proteomic approaches. *Food Chemistry: Molecular Sciences* 4: 100088. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fochms.2022.100088>
- Manolescu B, Atanasiu V, Cercasov C, Stoian I, Oprea E, Buşu C (2008) So many options but one choice: the human body prefers alpha-tocopherol. A matter of stereochemistry. *Journal of Medicine and Life* 1.
- Masterci F, Vassalle C, Chatzianagnostou K, Marabotti C, Siddiqui K, Eba AO, Mhamed SAS, Bandopadhyay A, Nazzaro MS, Passera M, Pingitore A (2017) Undernutrition and overnutrition burden for diseases in developing countries: The role of oxidative stress biomarkers to assess disease risk and interventional strategies. *Antioxidants* 6(2): 41. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox6020041>
- Mendiara SN, Perissinotti LJ (2017) β Carotene and Free Radical Reactions with Nitrogen Oxides. In: *Carotenoids*. <https://doi.org/10.5772/67683>
- Mey J (2017) RAR/RXR mediated signaling. In: *Gene Regulation, Epigenetics and Hormone Signaling*. Wiley, 457–510. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527697274.ch16>
- Miazek K, Beton K, Śliwińska A, Brożek-Pluska B (2022) The Effect of β -Carotene, Tocopherols and Ascorbic Acid as Anti-Oxidant Molecules on Human and Animal In Vitro/In Vivo Studies: A Review of Research Design and Analytical Techniques Used. *Biomolecules* 12(8): 1087. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom12081087>

- Mueller L, Boehm V (2011) Antioxidant activity of β -carotene compounds in different in vitro assays. *Molecules* 16(2): 1055–1069. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules16021055>
- Nagib MM, Tadros MG, Rahmo RM, Sabri NA, Khalifa AE, Masoud SI (2019) Ameliorative Effects of α -Tocopherol and/or Coenzyme Q10 on Phenytoin-Induced Cognitive Impairment in Rats: Role of VEGF and BDNF-TrkB-CREB Pathway. *Neurotoxicity Research* 35: 451–462. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12640-018-9971-6>
- Ngo V, Duennwald ML (2022) Nrf2 and Oxidative Stress: A General Overview of Mechanisms and Implications in Human Disease. *Antioxidants* 11(12): 2345. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11122345>
- Ohkatsu Y, Kajiyama T, Arai Y (2001) Antioxidant activities of tocopherols. *Polymer Degradation and Stability* 72(2): 303–311. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910\(01\)00022-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910(01)00022-2)
- Palozza P (2005) Can β -carotene regulate cell growth by a redox mechanism? An answer from cultured cells. In: *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta – Molecular Basis of Disease*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbadis.2004.12.008>
- Palozza P, Serini S, Di Nicuolo F, Piccioni E, Calviello G (2003) Prooxidant effects of β -carotene in cultured cells. *Molecular Aspects of Medicine* 24(6): 353–362. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0098-2997\(03\)00031-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0098-2997(03)00031-1)
- Pardede E, Julianti E, Siahaan FR, Harefa CV (2024) Antioxidant Activity, Ascorbic Acid, and Beta Carotene of Sumatran Red Tampoi (*Baccaurea costulata*) and Rambai (*Baccaurea motleyana*) Fruits. *Agro Bali: Agricultural Journal* 7: 708–718. <https://doi.org/10.37637/ab.v7i3.1980>
- Park HA, Hayden MM, Bannerman S, Jansen J, Crowe-White KM (2020) Anti-apoptotic effects of carotenoids in neurodegeneration. *Molecules* 25(15): 3453. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25153453>
- Pisoschi AM, Pop A (2015) The role of antioxidants in the chemistry of oxidative stress: A review. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 97: 55–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2015.04.040>
- Pizzino G, Irrera N, Cucinotta M, Pallio G, Mannino F, Arcoraci V, Squadrito F, Altavilla D, Bitto A (2017) Oxidative Stress: Harms and Benefits for Human Health. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity* 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/8416763>
- Prasad KN, Chew LY, Khoo HE, Yang B, Azlan A, Ismail A (2011) Carotenoids and antioxidant capacities from *Canarium odontophyllum* Miq. fruit. *Food Chemistry* 124(4): 1549–1555. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2010.08.010>
- Reiter E, Jiang Q, Christen S (2007) Anti-inflammatory properties of α - and γ -tocopherol. *Molecular Aspects of Medicine* 28(5–6): 668–691. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mam.2007.01.003>
- Ribeiro D, Freitas M, Silva AMS, Carvalho F, Fernandes E (2018) Antioxidant and pro-oxidant activities of carotenoids and their oxidation products. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 120: 681–699. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2018.07.060>
- Rohmah M, Rahmadi A, Raharjo S (2022) Bioaccessibility and antioxidant activity of β -carotene loaded nanostructured lipid carrier (NLC) from binary mixtures of palm stearin and palm olein. *Heliyon* 8(2): e08913. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e08913>
- Saha D, Mehndiratta M, Aaradhana, Shah D, Gupta P (2022) Oxidative Stress, Mitochondrial Dysfunction, and Premature Ageing in Severe Acute Malnutrition in Under-Five Children. *Indian Journal of Pediatrics* 89: 558–562. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12098-021-03981-5>
- Salim S (2017) Oxidative stress and the central nervous system. *Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics* 360(1): 201–205. <https://doi.org/10.1124/jpet.116.237503>
- Salmina AB, Gorina YV, Komleva YK, Panina YA, Malinovskaya NA, Lopatina OL (2021) Early life stress and metabolic plasticity of brain cells: Impact on neurogenesis and angiogenesis. *Biomedicines* 9(9): 1092. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines9091092>
- Samsonov A, Urlacher SS (2025) Oxidative Stress in Children and Adolescents: Insights Into Human Biology. *American Journal of Human Biology* 37(1): e24200. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajhb.24200>
- Selamat SN, Muhamad II, Idham Z, Pae N (2018) Retention of alpha Tocopherol and antioxidant activity of encapsulated palm mixed Vitamin E in formulated blends. *MOJ Food Processing & Technology* 6(3): 272–278. <https://doi.org/10.15406/mojfpt.2018.06.00175>
- Selvaraju TR, Khaza'ai H, Vidyadaran S, Mutalib MSA, Vasudevan R (2014) The neuroprotective effects of tocotrienol rich fraction and alpha tocopherol against glutamate injury in astrocytes. *Bosnian Journal of Basic Medical Sciences* 14(4): 195–204. <https://doi.org/10.17305/bjbms.2014.4.91>
- Shin J, Song M-H, Oh J-W, Keum Y-S, Saini RK (2020a) Pro-oxidant Actions of Carotenoids in Triggering Apoptosis of Cancer Cells: A Review of Emerging Evidence. *Antioxidants* 9: 532. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox9060532>
- Shin J, Song MH, Oh JW, Keum YS, Saini RK (2020b) Pro oxidant actions of carotenoids in triggering apoptosis of cancer cells: A review of emerging evidence. *Antioxidants* 9(6): 532. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox9060532>
- Singh AA, Katiyar S, Song M (2025) Phytochemicals Targeting BDNF Signaling for Treating Neurological Disorders. *Brain Sciences* 15: 252. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci15030252>
- Singh U, Jialal I (2004) Anti inflammatory Effects of α Tocopherol. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* 1031: 195–203. <https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1331.019>
- Soliman A, De Sanctis V, Alaaraj N, Ahmed S, Alyafei F, Hamed N, Soliman N (2021) Early and long-term consequences of nutritional stunting: From childhood to adulthood. *Acta Biomedica* 92(1): 11346. <https://doi.org/10.23750/abm.v92i1.11346>
- Song Y, Zhu L, Zheng X (2024) β -carotene inhibits MAPKs signaling pathways on rat colonic epithelial cells to attenuate TNF- α -induced intestinal inflammation and injury. *Cell Biochemistry and Biophysics* 82: 291–302. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12013-023-01202-8>
- Taufiqrokhman T (2023) Equality Strategy for Reducing Stunting Prevalence Rate: Case Study of DKI Jakarta Province. *Jurnal Bina Praja* 15(3): 495–506. <https://doi.org/10.21787/jbp.15.2023.495-506>
- Thbayh DK, Menten D, Boros ZR, Palusiak M, Farkas L, Viskolcz B, Fiser B (2024) α -Tocopherol and Trolox as Effective Natural Additives for Polyurethane Foams: A DFT and Experimental Study. *Molecules* 29: 6037. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules29246037>
- Traber MG, Atkinson J (2007) Vitamin E, antioxidant and nothing more. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine* 43(1): 4–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2007.03.024>
- Ulatowski L, Manor D (2013) Vitamin e trafficking in neurologic health and disease. *Annual Review of Nutrition* 33: 87–103. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-nutr-071812-161252>
- United Nations Children's Fund, World Health Organization, World Bank (2023) UNICEF, WHO, World Bank Level and trend in child malnutrition: Key findings of the 2023 edition of the joint child malnutrition estimates.
- Veleri S (2024) Malnutrition-Induced Oxidative Stress in Nervous System and Its Health Implications. In: *Adaptation under Stressful Environments through Biological Adjustments and Interventions*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-7652-2_17

- Wallert M, Ziegler M, Wang X, Maluenda A, Xu X, Yap ML, Witt R, Giles C, Kluge S, Hortmann M, Zhang J, Meikle P, Lorkowski S, Peter K (2019) α -Tocopherol preserves cardiac function by reducing oxidative stress and inflammation in ischemia/reperfusion injury. *Redox Biology* 26: 101292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.redox.2019.101292>
- Wang Y, Liang J, Xu B, Yang J, Wu Z, Cheng L (2024) TrkB/BDNF signaling pathway and its small molecular agonists in CNS injury. *Life Sciences* 336: 122282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lfs.2023.122282>
- Wu S, Chen R, Chen J, Yang N, Li K, Zhang Z, Zhang R (2023) Study of the Anti-Inflammatory Mechanism of β -Carotene Based on Network Pharmacology. *Molecules* 28(22): 7540. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28227540>
- Yamauchi R (1997) Vitamin E: Mechanism of Its Antioxidant Activity. *Food Science and Technology International, Tokyo* 3(4): 301–309. <https://doi.org/10.3136/fsti9596t9798.3.301>
- Yamauchi R (2007) Addition Products of α -Tocopherol with Lipid-Derived Free Radicals. *Vitamins and Hormones* 76: 309–327. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0083-6729\(07\)76011-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0083-6729(07)76011-9)
- Yang H, Kuhn C, Kolben T, Ma Z, Lin P, Mahner S, Jeschke U, von Schönfeldt V (2020) Early life oxidative stress and long-lasting cardiovascular effects on offspring conceived by assisted reproductive technologies: A review. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 21(15): 5175. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21155175>
- Yeh SL, Wang HM, Chen PY, Wu TC (2009) Interactions of β -carotene and flavonoids on the secretion of pro-inflammatory mediators in an in vitro system. *Chemico-Biological Interactions* 179(2–3): 386–393. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbi.2008.12.006>
- Yin B, Barrionuevo G, Batinic-Haberle I, Sandberg M, Weber SG (2017) Differences in Reperfusion-Induced Mitochondrial Oxidative Stress and Cell Death between Hippocampal CA1 and CA3 Subfields Are Due to the Mitochondrial Thioredoxin System. *Antioxidants and Redox Signaling* 27(9): 534–549. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ars.2016.6706>
- Yuan TF, Gu S, Shan C, Marchado S, Arias-Carrión O (2015) Oxidative Stress and Adult Neurogenesis. *Stem Cell Reviews and Reports* 11: 706–709. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12015-015-9603-y>
- Zhao ZK, Yu HL, Liu B, Wang H, Luo Q, Ding XG (2016) Antioxidative mechanism of Lycium barbarum polysaccharides promotes repair and regeneration following cavernous nerve injury. *Neural Regeneration Research* 11(8): 1312–1321. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1673-5374.189197>
- Zheng WV, Xu W, Li Y, Qin J, Zhou T, Li D, Xu Y, Cheng X, Xiong Y, Chen Z (2022) Anti-aging effect of β -carotene through regulating the KAT7-P15 signaling axis, inflammation and oxidative stress process. *Cellular and Molecular Biology Letters* 27: 86. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s11658-022-00389-7>
- Zhou L, Ouyang L, Lin S, Chen S, Liu YJ, Zhou W, Wang X (2018) Protective role of β -carotene against oxidative stress and neuroinflammation in a rat model of spinal cord injury. *International Immunopharmacology* 61: 92–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intimp.2018.05.022>